

PROGRAMME AND ABSTRACT BOOK

XII International congress of Forum Herbulot
“Accelerating Biodiversity Research in the Southern Hemisphere”

27 – 31 January 2025
South Africa

NATURAL HISTORY
MUSEUM
STUTTART

SNSB

Zoologische
Staatsammlung
München

TABLE OF CONTENTS

PROGRAMME, SHORT GLANCE.....	4
PROGRAMME, DETAILS.....	5
PROGRAMME FOR ACCOMPANYING PERSONS, SHORT GLANCE.....	8
ABSTRACTS.....	9
GENERAL INFORMATION.....	40
PROGRAMME FOR ACCOMPANYING PERSONS.....	41
ALPHABETIC LIST OF PARTICIPANTS.....	43
INDEX.....	46
VENUE AND SHUTTLE SERVICE.....	47

PROGRAMME, short glance

Sunday, 26.1.2025

Arrival, accommodation, light trapping

Monday, 27.1.2025

Opening & welcome message

Presentations

Light trapping

Tuesday, 28.1.2025

Presentations

Game safari, including conservation info in the area

Light trapping

Wednesday, 29.1.2025

Presentations

Light trapping

Thursday, 30.1.2025

Visiting Ditsong Museum of Natural History, Pretoria

Presentations

Closure

Light trapping

Friday, 31.1.2025

Departure

PROGRAMME, details

Monday, 27.1.2025

10:00-10:10	Hermann Staude WELCOME MESSAGE
10:10-10:20	Axel Hausmann OPENING ADDRESS
10:20-10:30	Pasi Sihvonen & Louisa Staude OVERVIEW OF CONGRESS AND ACCOMPANYING PERSONS' PROGRAMS
10:30-10:40	Conclave staff PRACTICALITIES
10:40-11:30	Hermann Staude AN OVERVIEW OF THE STUDY OF SOUTHERN AFRICAN GEOMETROIDEA
11:30-12:00	COFFEE / TEA BREAK
12:00-12:40	David L. Wagner EVOLUTION, ECOLOGY AND BIOSYSTEMATICS OF GEOMETRID LARVAE
13:00-15:00	LUNCH & PREPARING SPECIMENS
15:00-15:20	Sei-Woong Choi PATTERNS OF DIVERSITY OF GEOMETRID MOTHS AT LOCAL AND NATIONAL LEVELS IN SOUTH KOREA
15:20-15:40	Sara La Cava GEOMETRIDS OF MAIN FOREST TYPES OF SOUTH ITALY
15:40-16:00	Axel Hausmann CFH - THE GLOBAL BIODIVERSITY COLLECTION OF GEOMETRIDAE, COLLECTION FORUM HERBULOT
16:00-16:40	COFFEE / TEA BREAK
16:40-17:00	STEVE COLLINS AFRICAN BUTTERFLY RESEARCH INSTITUTE (ABRI) THROUGH A DIFFERENT LENS.
18:00-open end	SETTING UP TRAPS FOR MOTH COLLECTING
20:00-21:00	DINNER

Tuesday, 28.1.2025

08:30-09:30	BREAKFAST
09:30-10:30	PREPARING SPECIMENS
10:30-10:50	Gia da Zucco EXPLORING DIVERSITY OF GENUS <i>EUPITHECIA</i> CURTIS, 1825 IN CALABRIA: FAUNISTIC, ECOLOGICAL AND TAXONOMIC INSIGHTS
10:50-11:10	Hossein Rajaei ONLINE CATALOGUE OF THE SUPERFAMILY GEOMETROIDEA, A PROGRESS REPORT
11:10-11:30	Feza Can CONTRIBUTION TO THE KNOWLEDGE OF THE GEOMETRIDAE (LEPIDOPTERA) IN SOUTH-WESTERN TÜRKIYE

11:30-12:00	COFFEE / TEA BREAK
12:00-12:20	Sei-Woong Choi GENETIC DIVERSITY IN ISLAND AND MAINLAND MOUNTAIN POPULATIONS OF TWO COMMON MOTH SPECIES, <i>ALCIS ANGULIFERA</i> (BUTLER, 1878) (GEOMETRIDAE) AND <i>HYDRIOLLODES MOROSA</i> (BUTLER, 1879) (EREVIDAE) IN SOUTHERN KOREA
12:20-12:40	Jannik Wagner INTEGRATIVE TAXONOMY, BIOGEOGRAPHY AND SPECIATION OF GEOMETRID MOTHS IN AFRICA: A WINDOW INTO EVOLUTIONARY PROCESSES GENERATING BIODIVERSITY
13:00-14:40	LUNCH & PREPARING SPECIMENS
14:40-15:00	Axel Hausmann THE GEOMETRID CAMPAIGN ON BOLD - AN UPDATE
15:00-15:40	COFFEE BREAK
16:00-18:30	Game safari, including conservation info in the area (Cost: R350.00/person, to be paid directly to Conclave)
18:30-open end	SETTING UP TRAPS FOR MOTH COLLECTING
20:00-21:00	DINNER
Wednesday, 29.1.2025	
08:30-09:30	BREAKFAST
09:30-10:40	PREPARING SPECIMENS
10:40-11:00	Pasi Sihvonen GENOMIC INSIGHTS INTO SPECIES DELIMITATION AND EVOLUTIONARY HISTORY OF MIMETIC <i>ALETIS</i> MOTHS IN THE AFROTROPICS (GEOMETRIDAE: STERRHINAE)
11:00-11:30	Lynn Katsoulis MOGALE'S GATE: HIGHLIGHTING THE INADEQUACIES OF SOUTH AFRICAN VEGMAPS FOR BIODIVERSITY RESTORATION PLANT SELECTION
11:30-11:50	Tanner Matson EXPLORING COSTA RICAN GEOMETRIDAE: DNA BARCODING AND LIFE HISTORY OPPORTUNITIES
11:50-12:30	COFFEE / TEA BREAK
12:30-12:50	Stefano Scalercio THE INFLUENCE OF ZONATION AND HABITAT TYPE ON GEOMETRID MOTH DIVERSITY IN AN ITALIAN COASTAL DUNE ECOSYSTEM
12:50-13:10	Sven Wiessner RANGE EXPANSIONS OF SOME GEOMETRID MOTHS IN THE EAST GERMAN FEDERAL STATE OF SAXONY IN THE PAST 15 YEARS
13:10-14:40	LUNCH & PREPARING SPECIMENS
14:40-15:00	Tanner Matson MONOGRAPH OF NORTH AMERICAN STAMNODINI (LARENTIINAE) NORTH OF MEXICO WITH MOLECULAR PHYLOGENY AND GLOBAL REASSESSMENT OF STAMNODINI GENERA

15:00-15:20	Catherine Byrne EVOLUTION OF THE AUSTRALIAN LEPIDOPTERA: SURVIVAL IN AN ARID CONTINENT
15:20-16:00	COFFEE BREAK
16:00-16:20	Pasi Sihvonen THE EVOLUTION OF DIURNALITY IN URANIIDAE MOTHS, AN UNUSUALLY COLOURFUL AND IRIDESCENT LINEAGE OF LEPIDOPTERA
18:00-open end	SETTING UP TRAPS FOR MOTH COLLECTING
20:00-21:00	DINNER
Thursday, 30.1.2025	
08:30-09:30	BREAKFAST
08:30-13:00	Visiting Ditsong Museum of Natural History, Pretoria, including: Welcome by museum staff Visit to Entomology department and entomology collection Visit to Museum exhibitions (cost R100.00) Bus return back to Conclave at 13:00
14:00-15:00	LUNCH & PREPARING SPECIMENS
15:00-15:20	Maria Heikkilä OLD LOOPERS: A CRITICAL RE-EXAMINATION OF KNOWN FOSSIL GEOMETRIDAE
15:20-15:40	Pritha Dey A COMPARATIVE 3D MORPHOMETRIC STUDY OF THE TYMPANAL ORGANS IN GEOMETRID MOTHS
15:40-16:20	COFFEE BREAK
16:20-16:40	Mikael Englund FROM DISCOVERY TO DESCRIPTION: DEMONSTRATING THE TAXONOMIC PROCESS WHEN UNKNOWN GEOMETRID MOTHS ARE FOUND (LEPIDOPTERA: GEOMETRIDAE)
16:40-17:30	Final words and plans for Forum Herbulot 2026
17:30-open end	SETTING UP TRAPS FOR MOTH COLLECTING
20:00-21:00	DINNER
Friday, 31.1.2025	
08:30-09:30	BREAKFAST
09:30-11:00	PREPARING SPECIMENS
11:00-	Check-out
13:30	Possibility to have lunch, can be arranged at own cost
SHUTTLE BUS TO OR TAMBO AIRPORT IN THE AFTERNOON	

VENUE AND SHUTTLE SERVICE

ADDRESS

The Conclave Country Lodge
Leeuwgedacht Conservancy
Property 31, Welgedacht
Dinokeng North, Pretoria
GPS coordination:
S25°29'38.5", E28°27'30.3"

Phone: 066 273 7506
Mobile: 082 780 0155
E-Mail: info@conclave.co.za
Website: www.theconclave.co.za

DIRECTIONS TO THE CONCLAVE:

- Travel on the N1 highway from JHB/PTA towards Bela-Bela/Pietersburg.
- Take the Sefako Makgatho (Montana, Pretoria) off-ramp turn right, passing under the freeway.
- Travel for ± 1 km (2nd Traffic light).
- Turn left onto the marked KwaMhalanga.
- Travel for ± 27 km.
- Turn left onto the Hammanskraal / Dinokeng North dirt road.
- Follow this road for 4.7 km and pass Rustic Gem (4 x 4 Track).
- Keep right as the road forks sharp to your left.
- The gate code for Leeuwgedacht conservancy (red gate) will be send to you via WhatsApp. Alternatively call 31 at the Gate.
- Keep straight ahead until you see The Conclave on your right-hand side, 1.2km through conservancy gate.
- The gate Code for The Conclave's gate (black gate) will be on the Welcome board on your right unless given through.

Shuttle service is available from O.R. Tambo International Airport (Johannesburg) to Conclave and back to O.R. Tambo

If you need shuttle service, send your arrival flight details (or pick-up location at the airport) for the 26th and departure date, time and location for the 30th or 31st by the **3rd of December 2024** to info@condave.co.za

- Shuttle service can be paid on arrival with check in on 26.1.
- Shuttle services prices are below (note: prices are per vehicle, not per person). Conclave will confirm the exact amount for each guest when all passenger details are available. We aim to book 13/22 seats to keep the costs as low as possible.

TYPE OF VEHICLE	NO OF PASSENGERS	PRICE PER VEHICLE (one way)	AFTER HOUR CHARGES 21:00-5:00	WAITING FEE Per hours
13-seater quantum	13 Pax max	R3640.00	R100.00 One way	R400.00 Per hour
22-seater sprinter	22 Pax max	R4950.00	R100.00 One way	R400.00 Per hour
Sedan	4 Pax max	R1880.00	R100.00 One way	R400.00 Per hour